

The Clinical Significance of Implant Stability Quotient (ISQ) Measurements: A Literature Review

Gaurav Gupta¹
 D.K Gupta²
 Priyanka Gupta³
 Devanshi Sankhla⁴

Professor¹
 Dept. of Paediatric & Preventive Dentistry
 Jaipur Dental College
 Private Practice
 Wisdom Dental Clinics,
 Jaipur, Rajasthan

Senior Consultant²
 Dept. of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Wisdom Dental Clinics,
 Jaipur, Rajasthan

Sr. Demonstrator³
 RUHSCDS
 Dept. of Pedodontics & Preventive Dentistry
 Govt Dental College
 Jaipur, Rajasthan

Associate Dentist⁴
 Wisdom Dental Clinics
 Jaipur

Abstract

Implant stability quotients (ISQ values) are obtained in dental clinical practice on non-invasive basis by resonance frequency measurement rapidly after surgical placement of implants. The ISQ-values are used as indicator for mechanical implant stability, and are believed to have predictive power for clinical outcome. It is aim of this review to provide synopsis of all factors described in the literature that influence ISQ measurements by performing an exhaustive literature review; moreover, this review aims at elucidating the key factors relevant for a rapid clinical predictive assessment. We searched systematically and exhaustively all major databases for publications relating to ISQ measurement methodology and for ISQ-influencing factor analyses. The reports identified were ordered in experimental (preclinical) studies and in clinical publications. We were able to identify 13 basic factors influencing ISQ-measurements. Among these, local bone quality, playing a key role in such measurements, was subdivided in four specific sub factors; thus a total of 17 individual factors was identified and reported to influence ISQ-measurements. A comprehensive list of these factors is provided in Table form. A critical analysis points out that only 6 of these factors are of a sound predictive power useful for a rapid clinical assessment; and only two of these factors appear to have a well-documented scientific basis.

Keywords:

Resonance frequency analysis ,ISQ ,Dental implants ,Influencing factors

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Gaurav Gupta
 Address - Sector - 10,
 Plot number - 15,
 Vidhya Dhar Nagar,
 Jaipur, Rajasthan
 Email - dr.gauravgupta99@gmail.com

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Introduction

Implantology is a field of dentistry that has been practiced since many years, thanks to the biological osteointegration principles of Branemark's protocol^[1]. The osteointegration, defined as “a direct structural and functional connection between the living bone and the surface of the load-carrying implant,” depends on an atraumatic surgery with the use of surgical motors with speed and torque control, sterile saline solution for irrigation, titanium biocompatibility, and implant primary stability^[2].

In 1973, Cameron et al. specified that the micromovements at the bone/implant interface could be tolerated up to a certain threshold between 50 and 150 μm ^[3]. Therefore, it was common opinion that the micromotions produced by early loading could affect bone healing and induce

fibrous tissue encapsulation instead of osteointegration. For this reason, according to the original Branemark's protocol, a non-loaded healing period of 3–6 months following implant placement was essential to achieve adequate implant stability before functional loading^[4].

To date, it has been clarified that the measurement of osteointegration can be approached in a quantitative manner, as primary stability and secondary stability are in an inverse relationship^[5]. During the postsurgical healing period, between the 20th and 60th days, there is a critical phase due to the peri-implant bone remodeling in which a decay of primary stability occurs in favor of osteointegration (Figure 1); this is a critical time as the implant could be exposed to a higher risk of micromovements, especially in D3 and D4 bone density.

Figure 1 :Graphical curve illustrating implant stability as a function of time immediately after placement. Primary implant stability, which is the mechanical stability, decreases in favor of the biological stability that is the osteointegration

Controlled immediate loading protocols have now been recognized as not interfering with the osteointegration process when applied under well-defined circumstances such as the D1/D2 bone density, in which a decay of primary stability and the insurgence of micromovements are not strong^[6-10].

In addition to bone quantity and quality, there are other parameters that may impact the primary implant stability and may play a decisive role for an immediate controlled load; these parameters can be summarized as follows: the implant design (diameter, length, tapered shape, and treated surface) and the surgical technique (underpreparation)^[11].

ISQ, or Implant Stability Quotient, is a scale from 1 to 100 and is a measure of the stability of an implant. The ISQ scale has a non-linear correlation to micro mobility. With more than 1400 scientific references, we now know that high stability means >70 ISQ, between 60-69 is medium stability and < 60 ISQ is considered as low stability. [Figure 2a,2b]

Figure 2a,2b:Representation of ISQ

Discussion

Principle: Resonance Frequency Analysis

This diagnostic method computes implant stability and bone density by vibrational and structural analysis in noninvasive manner^[12]. Two devices have been developed commercially to measure implant stability, one is electrical and other is based on magnetic principle. First method uses direct wire connection between transducer and resonance frequency analyzer. The second method based upon measurement of magnetic frequencies between transducer and resonance frequency analyzer by a wireless probe (Figures 1 and 2). Both methods are competent for measuring similar changes; however, the magnetic device results in higher ISQ value when measuring the stability of non-submerged dental implant (Figures 3-7)^[13].

Figure3: Osstell devices -Electrical and magnetic RFA based devices.

These methods can reveal considerable increase or decrease in implant stability which could not be appraised clinically. Various factors can affect the readings like

effective implant length (length of exposed threads and abutment height), implant shape and diameter and bone quality and quantity^[14].

Figure 4: Osstell Beacon cordless device: Electrical and magnetic RFA based devices.

Figure 5: Measurement of ISQ by advanced RFA bases magnetic Osstell device immediately after implant placement.

Figure 6: Measurement of ISQ by Osstell device 3 months after implant placement depicting good biologic stability.

Figure 7: Implant stability on abutment and platform level Resonance Frequency Analysis by Osstell (a) Implant platform (b) 1 mm microvunit (c) 5 mm microvunit.

Measuring implant stability by implant oscillation frequency of bone can be assessed by RFA. Meredith et al. 1998 described the non-invasive method of assessing implant stability by OSSTELL devices. In 1999, OSSTELL devices was designed by the Integration Diagnostics Ltd., Sweden. Over last few years, various types of Osstell devices have developed to extemporize the implant stability measurements, namely, OSSTELL™, OSSTELL Mentor, and OSSTELL ISQ.

In 2009 the last and latest generation of this device was developed, OSSTELL ISQ, which includes new control unit with probe connected to it by means of cable. These devices are gaining popularity due to reliability and ease of assessing implant stability. These measurements are independent of intra and inter observer variability and reproduce accurate results.

Nedir et al.^[15] estimated implant primary stability as an indicator of osseointegration. As per his study, ISQ value of more than 49 will osseointegrate over period of three months and those with values higher than 54 can be loaded immediately.

Primary stability of implants which was assessed through RFA using OSSTELL Mentor devices was underestimated to analyze comparability and reproducibility^[16]. Clinical trials concluded almost perfect replicability and high reliability of ISQ measurements with Osstell devices^[17]. ISQ measurement by OSSTELL Mentor device during immediate and delayed loading implant cases concluded that it offers an objective method to determine the implant stability and for immediate loading^[18].

Comparison of OSSTELL Mentor and OSSTELL ISQ in measuring implant stability was evaluated and the mean values of ISQ for OSSTELL ISQ and OSSTELL Mentor were 72.87 and 72.04 respectively, suggesting perfect compliance, consistency and recreatability between these devices^[19].

There are various factors which affect the ISQ readings like anatomical direction of measurement in patient's mouth, gender of patient, intraoral location of implant [20], sex of patient, immediate versus delayed implantation, diameter and length of implant, designing of implant, insertion torque^[21], bone type at the site of implant, contact

surface area of implant. Various research studies indicated the possible interplay of insertion torque and ISQ values. Insertion torque was introduced to assess primary stability of implant and accordingly plant the surgical procedure on solid backgrounds. Good cortical bone thickness results in increased ISQ values due to better osseointegration, whereas less thickness results in reduced stability and lesser ISQ. In last few decades immediate implant protocol has become more popular due to less clinical treatment time. If favorable preclinical condition exists, immediate implant results in almost similar ISQ values when compared to delayed implant procedures. After 3 months when loading begins in delayed implant cases, secondary stability equalizes to the level of ISQ values of similar magnitude as those achieved in primary stability phases.

In our practice we compared the ISQ values of successful implants at the time of loading and post operatively with the ISQ values of implant failure cases, which manifested significant difference in values. However, ISQ distributions at implant insertion denoted overlapping which indicated that there was no correlation among the data that could be used to predict successful osseointegration. The predictiveness of ISQ values were enigmatic^[22].

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